

<App Name> Instruction Manual for Android Wear

Part 1: Installation on your Android Wear

Open the Google Play Store on your Android Wear.

Click "Search" and enter "<App Name>" with the keyboard.

Install the app by clicking "Install". After a few moments, the app will be installed on your Android Wear and appear in the app list.

If you prefer to install the app via Computer, please refer to Appendix 2.

Part 2: Setup of the <App Name> App

Open the <App Name> app on your Android Wear.

You will be greeted with the above screen.

Click on "User Settings" to open the settings page.

In case you are prompted to allow notifications. Please allow notifications, as they are essential to the study.

The screen will show you the next time the survey is planned to show up, allows you to change the settings and you can manually start the survey (after setup).

Note: If you missed the notifications pop-over, please see Appendix 1 before continuing with the setup.

Please set your User ID.

Please enter your assigned ID into the app and confirm by pressing OK at the bottom left.

Please set your workday start time.

Please select one of the predefined options.

Note: If you do not start work at any of the presented options, please choose the nearest option after your actual start time.

Please do the same for your workday end time.

Please select all days on which you work.

Please set your desired notification time. This is when you will receive a notification (and email) to fill out your daily or weekly survey. It is up to you if you would like to fill out those surveys right when you end work, or if you would like to do so later in the evening.

Click "Save User Settings". The setup is now complete.

You can now exit the app by pressing the top right button on your Android Wear.

You will receive a notification when it is time to fill out a quick self-report questionnaire. Depending on your notification settings, it will either play a sound, vibrate, and/or just show the notification.

Part 3: Enabling Notifications from your Phone

Note that this step is crucial for the <App Name> app to work correctly.

For the notifications to show up (either vibrate or sound), please check the settings in the "Galaxy Wear" app on your Android phone.

Please click "Watch settings" and then "Notifications".

In the subsequent screen click "More".

In the Dropdown, select "All", since by default not all apps are displayed.

Scroll down to find the <App Name> app in the list of all applications installed.

Once you find it, make sure that the slider is turned on (see screenshot).

In the <App Name> App, you can test if notifications work by clicking on the "App version" label.

It will then schedule a test notification that should appear after 1 minute.

Note that after updating or re-installing the app, you might need to -re-set your notification settings as per the description above.

Part 4: Allow the Samsung Watch to Play Sounds for Survey Reminders

To avoid missing the notifications that will remind you to take the hourly survey, please set the Galaxy Watch to “sound” as follows:

To do this, swipe down from top to bottom and then click the icon until it shows “sound” (see screenshot).

In case you are receiving other notifications and the sound distracts you, please disable the notifications for other apps during the study (in the opposite way as described in Part 3). Alternatively and if you notice the survey reminder notifications, you can set it to “vibrate” (instead of “sound”).

Part 5: Answering the hourly Surveys

Click on “GO!” to start the self-report questionnaire.

Note: If you currently do not have time to fill out the questionnaire, you can press the postpone button.

The app will now guide you through a series of questions. Please answer them by clicking the circles accordingly.

For example, in the screenshot above, the user selected “somewhat high” as their productivity for the past hour.

Note: If you did not work during the past hour, please click “I didn't work”.

Please answer all questions, until you see the final screen.

You can close the app by clicking on the screen again.

You will receive a notification when it is time to fill out the next questionnaire.

Part 6: Uninstalling <App Name> from your Android Wear Smartwatch

Swipe up on the homescreen to open the app list.

In the app list, swipe until you see the <App Name> app (green icon on the top left in the screenshot).

Tap and Hold the icon until the context menu shows up.

Select "Uninstall".

Confirm with "OK" to uninstall <App Name>.

Appendix 1: Installation of <App Name> from your Computer

Alternatively, you can visit the Google Play Store from your computer and install the app there:

1. Visit <App Link>

2. Click "Install" and sign-in if you're asked to.
3. In the pop-up, select your Android Wear watch and click "Install":

4. After a few moments, the app will be installed on your phone. Make sure the phone is connected to the internet (either via e-sim or via Bluetooth connection to your phone).

We thank you for your participation in this study. Should you have questions or need assistance at any time, please do not hesitate to reach out to <PI Name>